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WILD AND MANAGED *APIS MELLIFERA MELLIFERA*
ON ISLE DE GROIX, FRANCE

Colonie selvatiche e gestite di Apis mellifera nell'Isola di Groix, Francia

The European dark bee *Apis mellifera mellifera* is native to Northern Europe and populations of this bee subspecies are threatened by the introduction of other subspecies of honey bee that interbreed with the dark bee. It is rare to find a population that is relatively pure dark bee, that is also surrounded by managed *Apis*. One such location is Isle de Groix off the coast of Brittany, France. A study done in France, reported that the bees on Île de Groix were of highly dark bee genetics, unlike other locations in France which are hybrids of many races (HENRIQUES *et al.*, 2018). Two other aspects of the bees of Groix are that they live without treatment for *Varroa* mites and the beekeeping on the island is also of a “hands off” approach style. On Groix, the *Association pour la Sauvegarde de l'Abeille Noire* (ASAN.GX) is dedicated to the preservation of the dark bees. So how do the managed and wild colonies interact? Colony survival for wild colonies was monitored over 10+ years by ASAN.GX and for two years the managed colonies were monitored for survival and *Varroa* levels. Wild colonies lived on average 2.28 years (range of 1-10 years). Wild colony density has remained relatively consistent at about 1-2 colonies per hectare but the number of apiaries with managed colonies on the island continues to increase from 16 in 2008 to 42 in 2020. Is the carrying capacity of the island being exceeded by this increase in managed colonies? Even the beekeepers feel that too many managed honey bee colonies are not natural and could be impacting the other pollinators on the island. It appears that the managed bees and the free-living honey bees are all the same population as queens are not imported and both groups of bees

swarm readily. More studies should be conducted on the interactions of the managed and wild colonies on Isle de Groix. Because of the unique island isolation and the purity of the *Apis mellifera mellifera* bees, efforts are being made to seek legal protection of Groix as a pollinator refuge in the hopes that the islands' isolation from other populations and the traditional beekeeping practiced there can be preserved.

REFERENCES

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